

Analysis of the Influence of Natural Bathing Tourism Destinations on Village MSME Income Rumah Galuh Kabupaten Langkat

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ARTICLE INFO

Key Words : Facilities, Number of Visitors, Promotion, Capital, Income of MSMEs

Received : 03, January

Revised : 18, January

Accepted: 22, February

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ABSTRACT

Tourism generates demand for goods and services, leading to various industries such as craft, consumer products, service, and restaurants. Langkat Regency, particularly in Sei Bingai District, has numerous tourist attractions, including Pelaruga natural baths and seven angels in Rumah Galuh Village. However, these attractions face obstacles such as lacking a Base Transceiver Station (BTS), public toilets, visitor huts, and promotions. Additionally, infrastructure such as roads, electricity networks, clean water, and communications networks is lacking. This research aims to analyze capital factors, business location, type of merchandise, selling price, promotion, infrastructure, and number of visitors relevant to the income of MSMEs in Rumah Galuh Village, Langkat Regency. Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) is used to analyze data. Results show that facilities and infrastructure, number of visitors, promotion, and capital have a significant effect on MSMEs' income in Rumah Galuh Village, while business location, type of goods, and selling price have a negative effect. The results of simultaneous hypothesis testing show that facilities and infrastructure, number of visitors, promotion, and capital together have a positive and significant effect on MSMEs' income in Rumah Galuh Village

INTRODUCTION

The travel industry exercises encourage interest, both utilization and speculation, which will at last prompt the creation of labor and products. As a general rule, while voyaging, travelers will shop so it straightforwardly provokes interest (the travel industry's last interest) on the lookout for labor and products. Endeavors to fulfill vacationer needs require a few facilities like specialty enterprises, shopper items businesses, administration ventures, eateries or cafés, etc. The travel industry improvement as a feature of public improvement likewise has goals, including extending business valuable open doors and work open doors. By the phases of public turn of events, the execution of public the travel industry advancement is done in an extensive, adjusted, continuous, and economical way, advancement in the travel industry area has a definitive objective of expanding individuals' pay which can eventually work on individuals' government assistance.

North Sumatra, with its capital in Medan, is one of the provinces in Indonesia which has many tourism objects. North Sumatra is one of the provinces designated as a national tourist area because it has high biodiversity in the form of abundant natural resources. All existing natural potential has an important role in tourism development.

Langkat Regency is one of the districts in North Sumatra. Langkat Regency has many tourist attractions, but many of them have not been developed optimally. Among them is Sei Bingai District which has tourist attractions called Pelaruga Natural Baths, Seven Angels, and others in Rumah Galuh Village.

Along with the increasing number of tourist visits to the Pelaruga natural bathing tourist attraction, there are various kinds of obstacles, especially related to the facilities and infrastructure needed by tourists, such as the absence of a Base Transceiver Station (BTS) which functions as a means of telecommunications which is needed by tourists, toilets, general public, visitor huts, and promotions as well as in terms of infrastructure such as roads, electricity networks, clean water, and communications networks.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Income is compensation for providing services to other people, everyone gets income for helping other people. Meanwhile, personal income is all types of income, one of which is income earned without doing anything that is received by residents of a country. The pioneers of classical economics, Adam Smith and David Ricardo, stated that income was classified into three main social classes: workers, capital owners, and landowners. These three determine the 3 factors of production, namely labor, capital, and land. According to Georgi Mankiw, people's income is individual (personal income), namely income received by households and non-company economic businesses. Per capita income is the average income of the population of a country in a certain period, which is usually one year.

METHODOLOGY

This research uses the Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) method, this research lasts for 5 months from October 2023 to February 2024 starting from preparation to preparing the research, the data used uses primary data taken using questionnaires or questionnaires, the research location is in Rumah Galuh Village, Langkat Regency, North Sumatra.

RESULTS

The Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) method is used in the data analysis results to analyze groupings and then interpret them to get a true picture of the problem being studied. Then, factor examination is done which means figuring out how to sum up the data contained in the first (beginning) factors into another arrangement of aspects or factors (factors). The main thing to do is test Barlett's trial of Sphericity and Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO), which should be visible in the accompanying table:

Table 1. KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.670
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	48.760
	Df	28
	Sig.	.009

Source: Pengolahan SPSS versi 26.

The outcomes from Barleobtained's trial of Sphericity were 48.760 with a meaning of 0.009, this means that there is a relationship between factors (huge < 0.050). The consequences of the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) test got a worth of 0.633, which is above 0.5. Accordingly, the factors in this exploration can be handled further, by breaking down capital variables, business area, sort of product, selling cost, advancement, framework, number of guests, and pay of MSMEs in Rumah Galuh Town, Langkat Regime. Huge outcomes should be visible from the accompanying Turned Part Framework table:

Table 2. Rotated Component Matrix

	Component			
	1	2	3	4
Capital	.196	-.195	-.299	.707
Busin Location	.128	-.152	-.325	-.759
Types of goods	.738	.017	-.232	-.072
Selling price	.146	.536	-.021	-.031
Promotion	.006	-.029	.714	.047

Infrastructure	.781	.053	.248	.137
Number of visitors	-.363	.772	-.393	.117
MSME income	-.014	.600	.505	-.065

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.

a. Rotation converged in 7 iterations.

Source: Pengolahan SPSS version 26.

The Part Network coming about because of the turn cycle (Pivoted Part Lattice) shows a more clear and more sensible dispersion of factors. Deciding the variable contribution to a specific component depends on the greatness of the connection between the variable and the element, in particular to an enormous relationship. It is known, based on the results of the component matrix values, that out of the seven factors, four are suitable for influencing community welfare: a) Facilities and Infrastructure, which is the largest component with a value of 0.781 b) Component 2 biggest: Number of Guests with a worth of 0.772 c) Promotion, the third largest component, with a value of 0.714 d) The fourth biggest part: Capital with a worth of 0.707. The aftereffects of information examination show the consequences of speculation testing from this exploration, to see fractional theory testing and concurrent tests on factors applicable to MSME pay in Rumah Galuh Town. The consequences of the impact of the reliant variable on the autonomous variable should be visible in the accompanying table.

Table 3. Uji -t (Uji Hipotesis Partial) Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)	9.384	1.738		5.399	.000		
Infrastructure	.037	.076	.119	3.228	.000	.987	1.013
Number of visitors	.025	.077	.242	2.918	.004	.997	1.003
Premotion	.032	.069	.135	1.924	.007	.995	1.005
Capital	.031	.060	.180	2.164	.000	.990	1.010

a. Dependent Variable: MSME income

Source: Pengolahan SPSS versi 26.

In light of the table above it tends to be seen that: a) The t-determined worth of offices and foundation is $3.228 > 1.652$ then the sig esteem is $0.000 <$

0.05, so H_a is acknowledged and H_0 is dismissed, implying that the kind of merchandise is influential for the pay of Rumah Galuh Town MSMEs. b) The t-calculated value for the number of visitors is 2.918 more than or equal to 1.652, and the sig value is 0.004 less than or equal to 0.05. As a result, H_a is accepted and H_0 is rejected, indicating that the selling price has a significant impact on the income of MSMEs in Rumah Galuh Village. c) The t-determined worth of advancement is $1.924 > 1.652$ then the sig esteem is $0.007 < 0.05$, so H_a is acknowledged and H_0 is dismissed, implying that advancement is huge for the pay of Rumah Galuh Town MSMEs. d) The t-determined capital worth is $2.164 > 1.652$ then the sig esteem is $0.000 < 0.05$, so H_a is acknowledged and H_0 is dismissed, implying that capital is huge with the pay of Rumah Galuh Town MSMEs.

Table 4. F-Test (Simultaneous Hypothesis Test) ANOVAa

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	216.687	4	14.172	14.248	.003 ^b
	Residual	126.686	129	.982		
	Total	143.373	133			

a. Dependent Variable: MSMEs

b. Predictors: (Constant), Capital, Promotion, Number of Visitors, Facilities

Source: Pengolahan SPSS veverse6

Given the table above, it very well may be seen that the consequences of the ANOVA test with F (Fisher) examination show that the determined F esteem is $14.248 > F$ table 2.42 so H_a is acknowledged and H_0 is dismissed and this implies that the offices, number of guests, advancement and capital together altogether to the pay of Rumah Galuh Town MSMEs.

Table 5. Koefisien Determinasi (R^2) Model Summaryb

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.741 ^a	.416	.489	1.99099	1.339

a. Predictors: (Constant), Capital, Promotion, Number of Visitors, Facilities

b. Dependent Variable: MSMEs Income

Source: Pengolahan SPSS versi 26

Given the table above, it very well may be seen that the changed R Square figure is 0.489 which can be known as the coefficient of assurance, which for this situation implies that 48.9% of the pay of MSMEs in Rumah Galuh town can be gotten and made sense of by offices, foundation, number of guests, advancements and capital, while the rest is made sense of by different elements or factors outside the model that are not contemplated.

DISCUSSION

The consequences of the examination in Corroborative Component Investigation (CFA) show that from the made sense of change table, it very well may be seen that there are just 4 elements shaped. a) Facilities and Framework

affect the Pay of MSMEs in Rumah Galuh Town. Given the aftereffects of the Confirmatory Element Examination (CFA) the board of rotational result (Turned Part Network), shows that the biggest part 1 is offices and framework at 0.781, which deserves impacting MSME pay. So it very well may be presumed that offices and frameworks impact the pay of MSMEs in Rumah Galuh Town. This study's findings are consistent with those of Sugiyono (2017), who found that people's income in the Seribu Islands is positively and insignificantly influenced by the infrastructure variable. Aside from that, research from (Sammeang 2016) shows that the framework likewise makes a negative and irrelevant difference. on individuals' pay. Offices and foundation are critical for MSME pay in Rumah Galuh Town, since we realize that the offices and framework are satisfactory, doing the travel industry exercises will run ideally. By having suitable offices and framework, guests will increment and in this way, monetary exchanges will happen that can build the pay of individuals of Rumah Galuh Town. So along these lines, the offices and framework given at vacation spots and around local area business areas will be a thought for travelers to visit and will be something beneficial for the local area to build pay to meet their everyday requirements. Notwithstanding, research led by Sudiarta in 2016 expressed that offices and frameworks altogether affect individuals' pay. Aside from that, the consequences of this exploration are likewise as per past examination directed by (Zeithaml 2016) which expressed that foundation altogether affects individuals' pay. b) The number of guests affects the pay of MSMEs in Rumah Galuh Town. In light of the consequences of the Confirmatory Element Examination (CFA) the executives of the revolution yield (Pivoted Part Grid), show that the second biggest part is the number of guests at 0.772, which genuinely affects MSME pay. So it very well may be presumed that the quantity of guests essentially affects the pay of MSMEs in Rumah Galuh Town. This is following the consequences of exploration by (Junari 2019) which expresses that the variable number of guests altogether affects individuals' pay at Lakey Hu'u Ocean side The travel industry, Dompu Rule. "Analysis of Factors that Influence the Number of Visitors to the Siuri Beach Ecotourism Object, Toinasa Village, West Pamona District, Poso Regency," a study conducted by Arif and Sustri (2015), examines the factors that influence the number of visitors to the Siuri Beach Ecotourism Object. The reliant variable in this study is the quantity of visits. The exploration results show that the quantity of guests fundamentally affects pay. This condition is as per the field where an extremely enormous number of guests visit the travel industry in Rumah Galuh Town so it immensely affects the pay level of the local area. To build the number of guests we should advance the travel industry in Rumah Galuh Town through promoting or media so that meeting vacationers can figure it out. vacation destinations in Rumah Galuh Town. c) Promotion impacts the pay of MSMEs in Rumah Galuh Town Given the consequences of the Confirmatory Variable Examination (CFA) the board on rotational result (Pivoted Part Grid), shows that the third biggest part is advancement at 0.714, which truly deserves affecting MSME pay. So it tends to be reasoned that advancement fundamentally affects the pay of

MSMEs in Rumah Galuh Town. This is as per past exploration which demonstrates the way that special outcomes can expand the number of traveler visits to a vacationer location so it straightforwardly emphatically affects the pay of the local area around the vacation spot (Handayani and Dedi, 2017; Mardiyani and Murwatiningsih, 2015; Rahim, 2020; Setiyorini and Kristiyana, 2019). Given the outcomes in the field, show proof that the travel industry advancement that is imaginative, creative, appealing, and as per what has been arranged by the administration and neighborhood government and completed ideally, will consequently deliver acceptable outcomes, this will be significant in expanding local area pay and monetary advancement of the local area in Rumah Galuh Town. This situation should be arranged cautiously by the administration, nearby government, and local area with the ideal targets so the result or eventual outcome will likewise be as per the goals that have been set. Promoting Rumah Galuh Village's beauty and superiority to local and international tourists is supported by promotion. The more notable the objections in Rumah Galuh Town are, the more vacationers will be keen on visiting traveler locations which will affect the pay of the nearby local area and impact pay. With expanding pay, government assistance will increase. d)

Capital impacts the pay of MSMEs in Rumah Galuh Town. Given the consequences of the Confirmatory Variable Examination (CFA) the board on the rotational result (Pivoted Part Lattice), shows that the fourth biggest part is capital of 0.707, which genuinely deserves impacting MSME pay. So it very well may be presumed that capital altogether affects the pay of MSMEs in Rumah Galuh Town. This is by research results (Wulandari C., 2017) which express that business capital impacts dealers' pay. In the meantime, research led by (Widyastuti, 2018) states that the elements that impact dealers' pay are value, number of wards, business capital, and work. This condition is consistent with the area in which traders' income is significantly influenced by business capital. In Rumah Galuh Village, business owners must first have business capital, and these indicators also have an impact on their own capital and bank loans. For entrepreneurs in Rumah Galuh Town, this should be satisfied to have the option to acquire great deals and bring about requests to meet their day-to-day needs. Suyadi Prawirosentono expressed that in maintaining a business the main thing is capital, remembering for exchanging exercises. Capital is all types of abundance utilized in the creation cycle or delivering yield. The capital utilized can emerge out of individual capital, yet on the off chance that singular capital isn't adequate it very well may be enhanced with credit capital, so overall the kinds of capital that can be acquired to address capital issues comprise individual capital and advance capital. 2. The consequences of the speculation test investigation show: a) The Impact of Infrastructure on the Income of MSMEs. In light of the fractional speculation test, the t-count for offices and framework was $3.228 > 1.652$ then the sig esteem was $0.000 < 0.05$, so H_a was acknowledged and H_0 was dismissed, implying that the kind of merchandise was vital for the pay of Rumah Galuh Town MSMEs. The travel industry offices are offices that should be given assuming a vacationer region is to be created. In the interim, the foundation is a general framework, meaning it

isn't explicitly utilized for the travel industry purposes as it were. Foundation has a cozy relationship with vacationer fulfillment seen from the nature of the administration of a vacation destination. Administration quality is a unique condition connected with items, administrations, individuals, cycles, and conditions that meet or surpass traveler assumptions. With great assistance quality, it is feasible for travelers to feel happy with the nature of administration so vacationers become faithful and can expand the number of vacationer visits consequently expanding the pay of the encompassing local area.

b) The effect of the number of visitors on the income of MSMEs. Given the fractional speculation, the test did, the t-determined incentive for the number of guests was $2.918 > 1.652$ then the sig esteem was $0.004 < 0.05$, so H_a was acknowledged and H_0 was dismissed, implying that the selling cost was vital for the pay of the MSMEs in Rumah Galuh Town. The higher the number of guests in a business, the more noteworthy the chance of getting higher pay. It will result in an increase in revenue for the tourism-related business community due to the consumption of activities by both domestic and international tourists. In this way, the higher the progression of traveler visits, the pay of individuals in a space will likewise increment.

c) Effect of Advancement on MSME Pay. The promotion t-calculated value was $1.924 > 1.652$, and the sig value was $0.007 < 0.05$, indicating that H_a was accepted and H_0 was rejected by the partial hypothesis test. This indicates that promotion had a significant impact on the income of MSMEs in Rumah Galuh Village. With the travel industry advancement that is imaginative, creative, alluring, and as per what has been arranged by the administration and nearby government and did ideally, it will naturally deliver good outcomes, this will assume a significant part in expanding pay and propelling the local area's economy. Nonetheless, this should be settled upon cautiously by the administration and neighborhood pioneers and subordinates with the ideal objectives so the result or end-product will likewise be as per the objectives that have been set.

d) The Impact of Capital on MSME Pay. The t-calculated capital value was $2.164 > 1.652$, and the sig value was $0.000 < 0.05$, indicating that capital was significant with Rumah Galuh Village MSMEs' income and that H_a was accepted and H_0 was rejected based on the partial hypothesis test. Capital for business entertainers is one of the creation factors that impact pay levels. The size of the business capital utilized in the business will influence the pay procured by the business entertainer. This is as per the Cobb-Douglas hypothesis which expresses that capital impacts creation yield. Because the production process necessitates the expenditure of labor, as well as the purchase of raw materials and equipment, this demonstrates that the output of production is proportional to the capital invested.

e) The impact on MSME income that facilities, the number of visitors, promotions, and capital have. In light of the concurrent speculation test, the F-estimation esteem is $14.248 > F$ table 2.42 so H_a is acknowledged and H_0 is dismissed and this implies that offices, framework, number of guests, advancements, and capital are mutually vital for the pay of Rumah Galuh Town MSMEs. This study's findings demonstrate that capital, promotion, facilities and infrastructure, and the number of visitors all contribute significantly to

MSME income. A few marks of pay are capital, sort of merchandise, and selling cost. The more advancements made by dealers at vacation spots in Rumah Galuh Town, the more traveler visits will be at vacation destinations in Rumah Galuh Town and this will eventually impact the expansion of MSME pay. To draw in the consideration of travelers, you can do this by giving the best offices and keeping up with magnificence and tidiness so sightseers feel great. The public authority and exploration speakers from USU certainly stand out to work on supporting offices and frameworks in the travel industry area in Rumah Galuh Town, since this objective is one of the possibilities in the Langkat Regime. Working on the offices and foundation at the Rumah Galuh Town vacation destination can increment visits from sightseers. In addition, we must increase promotion through the use of social media, such as Instagram and Facebook stories, to provide quick access to information for the general public to promote tourist attractions and take part in events so that tourist attractions become more well-known to the community as a whole and can attract attention. Visit The travel industry in Rumah Galuh Town. Given this, it can expand the number of sightseers who will visit vacation destinations so the pay of brokers at vacation spots in Rumah Galuh Town can be expanded.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

From the aftereffects of exploration on factors that increment MSME pay in Rumah Galuh Town, Langkat Rule, and a few ends can be communicated as follows: 1) The CFA test on the KMO and Bartlett's Test tables shows that the information is legitimate and can be examined further with factor investigation. The Bartlett test esteem expresses that the connection network framed is a personality grid, or as such, the component model utilized is great and in the Pivoted Framework table it is known that of the eight variables, 4 elements genuinely deserve impacting local area government assistance which affect the pay of MSMEs in the town. Galuh house, Langkat Regime, in particular offices and framework, number of guests, advancement and capital. 2) Results The consequences of the halfway speculation test show that offices and foundations make a massive difference, then MSME pay will build, the quantity of guests makes a huge difference, then MSME pay will increment, advancement makes a tremendous difference, then MSME pay will increment, capital makes a tremendous difference, then, at that point, MSME pay will increment. 3) The consequences of synchronous speculation testing show that offices, foundation, number of guests, advancements, and capital affect MSME pay in Rumah Galuh Town, Langkat Regime.

FURTHER STUDY

This research still has limitations so further research on the topic still needs to be done "Analysis of the Influence of Natural Bathing Tourism Destinations on Village MSME Income."

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